

An analysis of capillary blood glucose levels in hospitalized patients with stroke

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Abstract:

Background and Aims:

People with acute stroke and diabetes mellitus may have episodes of hypoglycaemia (capillary blood glucose (CBG) <4mmol/l) and hyperglycaemia (CBG > 15 mmol/l). Capillary blood glucose (CBG) levels may also vary within these more extreme ranges. We aimed to examine the relationship between episodes of hypoglycaemia, hyperglycaemia and variability in CBG (CBGv) with outcome in hospitalised patients with diabetes and acute stroke.

Method :

We used routinely available clinical data from Scottish National Health Service records and from the Scottish Stroke Care Audit. All CBG measurements during a verified stroke admission were identified and episodes of hypoglycaemia and hyperglycaemia identified. CBGv was defined as the interquartile range (IQR) of all recorded CBG readings during the admission. We extracted outcome data for death, readmission to the hospital, and discharge destination and assessed the relationship with CBG measures using Cox-proportional hazards models and logistic regression.

Results :

We included 3551 patients. Hypoglycaemia, hyperglycaemia and CBGv were associated with increased risk of death (HR=1.3;1.05–1.6, HR=2.06;1.7–2.5, HR=1.13;1.09–1.17 respectively). Hypoglycaemia was associated with lower rate of readmission (HR=0.85;0.70–0.10,p<0.04) and CBGv with an increase (HR=1.04,1.01–1.07,p<0.001). The number of hypoglycaemic episodes (≥ 4) was associated with discharge to a destination other than (OR 2.25;1.45– 3.5,p<0.001).

Conclusion :

Outcomes were worse in patients with stroke and diabetes who had episodes of hypoglycaemia, hyperglycaemia and greater CBGv. Close monitoring of blood glucose levels is needed along with strategies to minimise the number of episodes of hypoglycaemia and variability of blood glucose levels.

Key Words :

Capillary blood glucose, Hypoglycaemia, Hyperglycaemia, Stroke, Diabetes mellitus.

Detection of diabetes early after stroke using the HbA1c

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Abstract:

Background and Aims:

People with acute stroke should be screened for the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus. This can be done using a variety of tests including fasting glucose levels, an oral glucose tolerance test and levels of glycosylated haemoglobin. We assessed the incidence of diabetes mellitus in people with acute stroke using HbA1c levels during admission and HbA1c levels and an OGTT at 3 months after admission.

Method:

People with acute stroke within 14 days and no history of DM were enrolled. HbA1c levels were checked at baseline. At 3 months participants returned for a second HbA1c level and an oral glucose tolerance test. HbA1c results were categorised into three groups according to American Diabetes Association (ADA) standards of care for diabetes (normal, HbA1c <39 mmol/mol, prediabetic, HbA1c 39-47 mmol/mol, diabetic > 48 mmol/mol). The performance of HbA1c for detecting DM was evaluated by receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis.

Results:

Among 94 patients, 27 were prediabetic and four were diagnosed with DM. Of 46 patients who completed second HbA1c and OGTT, 14 were prediabetic and one was diagnosed with DM. A baseline HbA1c value of ≥ 39 mmol/mol detected prediabetic and DM with a 57.1% sensitivity and a 53.9% specificity compared with the OGTT results. Comparing the measurements of the baseline HbA1c value with the fasting plasma glucose level (FBG) (>6.0 mmol/L) increased the sensitivity to 100% and 72.1% specificity.

Conclusion:

The total prevalence of DM and prediabetic were substantially higher based on HbA1c values than based on OGTT and FBG. Further studies on stroke patients are needed to evaluate using routine HbA1c and its potential for predicting DM and future clinical development of stroke disease.

Hallucination in patients with Alzheimer's disease and neuronal hyperactivity in the brain regions associated with sensory perception processing and recall

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Abstract:

According to brain imaging studies on hallucinations, the direct brain stimulation study and the study of dreams, we proposed the main cause of hallucinations is the abnormal activity in the brain regions associated with sensory perception processing and recall. While the complex and vivid illusions come from an abnormal activity at the high-level sensory processing brain region, the activities in the primary sensory brain region can produce a simple illusion of content. Hallucinations, specifically, are associated with impairments from the bottom-up or top-down processing, deficits in memory recall, and source attribution failures.

The cortical atrophy and white matter lesions in some brain areas that are connected to hallucinations are found in brain image studies from patients with both AD and hallucinations. The atrophy of supramarginal gyrus, occipital cortex, and white matter lesions relate to the impairments from the bottom-up processing. The atrophy of lateral frontal, posterior cingulate cortex, superior frontal gyrus, and lingual gyrus involve with the deficits in memory recollection processes. The atrophy of anterior cingulate and the insula connect with the source attribution failures. The neuronal injury have been related to the neuronal hyperactivity in AD. A study by Busche et al. shows that the direct application of soluble A β could induce neuronal hyperactivity in the hippocampus of wild type mice, which is crucial direct evidence for hippocampal hyperactivity induced by soluble A β . Then, according to Stargardt et al., in the presymptomatic stages of sporadic and familial AD, neuronal hyperactivity—an early phenotype in mouse models and humans with AD—plays a major role in the development of neurodegeneration. Later, according to Nuriel et al., they also identified an APOE4-associated hyperactivity phenotype within the brains of APOE mice. They found that the neuronal hyperactivity is caused by decreasing background inhibition, which reduces the responsiveness of excitatory neurons to GABAergic inhibitory inputs. Moreover, in an additional study, Lerskrai et al. discovered that presynaptic calcium ion storage is a key factor intercalling A D - relatedneural hyperactivity, which could be used as a treatment target for this abnormal activity. Therefore, we speculate that the neuronal hyperactivity in the AD brain not only causes atrophy of the cortex but also causes hallucinations when the neuronal hyperactivity occurs in brain regions, which are associated with sensory perception processing and sensory memory recalling. In other words, the neuronal hyperactivity is the link between cortical atrophy and hallucinations. Thus, the inhibition of neuronal hyperactivity in AD could be the treatment target for hallucination in AD patients.

Keywords:

Alzheimer's disease, hallucination, neuronal hyperactivity, sensory perception, sensory memory recall.

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Widespread Deficits in Cortical Circuits in Early Phase Schizophrenia: A Connectome Study

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Abstract:

Objective: Schizophrenia is considered a disorder of altered neural connections resulting in impaired information integration. Whole brain assessment of within- and between- cortical network connections may determine how information processing is disrupted in this illness.

Method: Patients with early-phase schizophrenia ($n = 56$) and a matched control sample ($n = 32$) underwent resting-state fMRI scans. Gray matter regions were organized into nine distinct functional networks. Time-series correlations between 278 gray matter regions were calculated, and network connectivity properties were defined by the mean and variance of correlations of all regions. Connectome measures of global efficiency (degree of interconnectivity) and locations of hubs (regions of high density connections) were also calculated.

Results: The control sample had greater connectivity between the following network pairs: somatomotor-limbic, somatomotor-default mode, dorsal attention-default mode, ventral attention-limbic, and ventral attention-default mode. The patient sample had greater variance between ventral attention network connections and the other networks. Illness duration was associated with overall increases in the variability of network connections. The control group had higher global efficiency, and more hubs in limbic and cerebellum networks, while patient group hubs were more likely to be in visual, frontoparietal, or subcortical networks.

Conclusions: Reduced functional connectivity in patients was largely present between distinct networks, rather than within-networks. Greater metabolic demands of between-network connections may have contributed to these findings, as schizophrenia is purported to be associated with metabolic deficits leaving high demand structures vulnerable. Higher variance of between network connectivity in patients suggests disorganized communication patterns that increases with disease progression.

Pharmacological interventions targeting PI3K/AKT/GSK-3 β pathway of insulin signaling in intracerebroventricular-streptozocin model of Alzheimer's disease

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Abstract:

ICV-STZ was used for the model of sporadic Alzheimer's disease being established. Adult male Wistar rats (48) weighing 200-300 g bred in Central Animal House facility of Panjab University were used. Animals were randomly divided into 8 groups comprising 6 animals in each group as follows:

Protocol lasted for 21 days, sacrificing animals on 22nd day followed by isolation of serum and dissection of cortex and hippocampus, preserving the same for further analysis.

Behavioral studies like Morris water maze was done for assessing spatial memory, novel object recognition for associative memory and actophotometer was performed for locomotor activity.

Biochemical estimations for antioxidant activity or oxidative stress such as reduced glutathione estimation, superoxide dismutase assay, catalase assay, glutathione peroxidase assay, myeloperoxidase assay, glutathione S-transferase assay, lipid peroxidation assay, and protein carbonylation assay were performed in the homogenates of cortex and hippocampus of the brain which are the specific regions for memory, learning and cognition. For nitrosative stress, nitrite estimation was done. Protein concentrations were determined by the biuret method. Cholinergic activity was evaluated by acetylcholinesterase assay to assess the cholinergic dysfunction which is one of the core pathologies of dementia and AD. Inflammatory cytokines like TNF- α , IL-6 was determined by ELISA method to evaluate the neuroinflammation which is aggravated by insulin resistance. C-reactive protein, a marker of neuroinflammation and neurodegeneration was also determined by ELISA. Mitochondrial dysfunction was evaluated estimating mitochondrial enzyme complex-I, II, III, IV depicting picture of viable and non-viable neuronal cells.

Histopathology was done by H&E staining to find out apoptotic cells, neuroinflammation, and neurodegeneration.

Molecular techniques like western blotting for p-tau, amyloid-beta, Akt protein and RT-PCR for PI3-K, AKT, p-AKT, and GSK 3- β was performed for gene expression analysis.

Key Words:

ICV-STZ, PI3-K/AKT/GSK3- β , Insulin resistance, neuroinflammation, Cognition,

Late post partum eclampsia complicated with Posterior Reversible Encephalopathy Syndrome (PRES): A Case Series

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Abstract:

Recently, there have been increasing reports of Posterior Reversible Encephalopathy Syndrome (PRES) occurring in pregnant or postpartum patients with or without history of gestational hypertension or preeclampsia. This study provides a brief overview on the etiology, epidemiology, and pathophysiology of PRES which remains a subject of debate. The rest of the report focuses on the course, diagnosis, management and prognosis of PRES in patients presenting with late onset postpartum eclampsia with an initial presentation of headache, seizures, or visual symptoms. All patients were diagnosed through cranial MRI. Rigorous management for hypertension was done as well as seizure control. These patients were noted to have improved overall outcome on discharge as well as on follow-up.

Key Words:

Posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome; PRES; preeclampsia; eclampsia; late post partum eclampsia; seizures

Strategy of Targeted Pharmacological Regulation of Intracellular Signal Transduction in Regenerative-Competent Cells - a New Direction of Therapy in Regenerative Medicine

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Abstract:

Advances in the field of cellular technologies have led to the possibility of developing a new direction of targeted therapy in regenerative medicine - "Strategy of Pharmacological Regulation of Intracellular Signal Transduction in Regenerative-competent Cells" (Patent RU № 2599289, 2016). The role of NF- κ B, IKK, PKC, PKB, PI3K, ERK 1/2, p38, adenylate cyclase, PKA, JAKs, STAT3, JNK, p53 in the realization of functioning progenitor elements of different classes and cells of tissue microenvironment was studied in vitro by means of cultural, immunological and other methods. On the models of posthypoxic encephalopathy, skin wound and cytostatic myelosuppression in experimental animals the therapeutic effects and mechanisms of action of modifiers of signal molecules activity were studied. The specificity of the involvement of a number of signaling molecules in the regulation of cell cycle and development of progenitor cells of various classes, as well as in the production of humoral factors by microenvironment cells was revealed. The neuroregenerative effects of JNK inhibitors associated with activation of neural stem cells of brain were shown on the model of encephalopathy. An algorithm and approaches for estimating the potential efficiency and many-sided selectivity of the modifiers of signaling molecules activity as targeted hemostimulators were developed. The effectiveness of various targeted pharmacological agents determined by the selective effect on different types of regenerative-competent cells was demonstrated on the models of cytostatic myelosuppression of various genesis. The perspective of using intracellular signaling molecules in regenerative-competent cells as targets of drugs for regenerative medicine was shown.

Key Words:

Pharmacological targets, regenerative medicine, stem cells, progenitors, microenvironment, signaling pathways, pharmacology, drugs.

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the participation of signaling molecules in the stimulation of proliferation multipotential mesenchymal stem cells. Simple arrows: intracellular pathways involved in activation of functions of mesenchymal precursors under optimal vital activity; dotted arrows: pathways of suppression of mesenchymal precursor cells; thick arrows: pathways of activation functions of mesenchymal progenitor cells under the influence of regulatory factors (redundant pathways).

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Management of the Type 3 Diabetics Mellitus Migraine, insomnia sleep apnea and to prevent the neurological distrobencies for foetus with the help of Dental Sleep Medicine

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Abstract:

Type three diabetics mellitus is the condition where the brain cells do suffer from the condition where the glucose dosen't enter into the brain cells and the reasons are panchriatic insulin cannaot enter into the blood brain barrier that is why brain produces its own insulinthe cells which produce insulin for the brain cells are called as Dilip 2.3 and 5 cells (Rat Neurons) which are located near Serotonin 5-HT1A receptors either the functional aspect of these Cells Becoming reduced or increasing the insulin Resistancy of the brain cells becoming reduced which can be easily predicted in those condition where improper induction of NREM stage 3 & 4 and REM sleeps

Migraine is calles as vascular head ache but the articals demonstrated that the mainreacon of the abnormalfunction of the Vescles is due to the improper induction of NREM stage 3&4 sleeps

Co existence of sleep apnea for the mother leads to the neurological distrobencies for the mother as well as the foetus

Insomnia and sleep apnea are well known sleep diorders

Key Words:

Type 3 diabetics mellitus, migrene, insomnia, sleep apnea, neurological distrobancies for the both mother and foetus can be easily managed with the help of dental sleep medicine with tne more higher success rate through medical, surgical and appliance management

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the insulin production mechanism of the brain

References:

1. Dr. Brain palmer articles
2. DR. Balakishan Jayan articals

Knowledge, Practice and Attitude towards Epilepsy and Associated Factors among Adults in Goncha Siso Enesie Woreda Rural Kebeles

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Abstract:

Back ground: Epilepsy is one of common neurological disorder in developing countries. Epilepsy affects 50 million people worldwide, and 80% of them live in the developing world. Epilepsy is one of stigmatizing problem with social, physical, economical and psychological effects on the patient as well as on the family.

Objective: To assess Knowledge, Practice and Attitude about Epilepsy and associated factors among Adults in Goncha Siso Enesie Woreda Rural Kebeles, East Gojjam, Ethiopia, 2016.

Method: Community based cross-sectional study design was used. The study was conducted from 2 September 2016 to 24 October 2016. In this study, sample size was 634 households from randomly selected kebele. To assess the relationship of factors and with the dependent variables multiple logistic regression analysis was performed.

Result: A total of 600 respondents were interviewed. This made the response rate to be 94.6%. One hundred percent of participants replied as they heard about Epilepsy from different sources previously. Even though they have awareness, about 285(47.5%) have inadequate knowledge, 379(63.2%) poor Practice, 206(34.3%) have unfavorable attitude towards epilepsy. Participants who have educational status of college and above are 3.5 times have favorable attitude than participants who could not read and write.

Conclusion: The main finding of this study indicates medium adequate knowledge, high poor Practice and high favorable attitude about epilepsy. The findings indicate, they were familiar with epilepsy, yet there is still problem with practice. Determinate variables for knowledge are educational level, residency and walking time between home and health institution and for practice educational status and family role are significant. Educational status also affects attitude of participants. All stalk holders of Goncha Siso Enesie Woreda and all health institutions shall work integrated on creation of awareness on interventions which are important when they encounter epileptic patient

Prediction of Inhibitory Effects of Dietary Fruit Flavanoids Against Vascular Dementia Targets-A Molecular Docking Approach

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Abstract:

Flavonoids are widely distributed in edible fruits and vegetables with a broad range of pharmacological and biological activities 1-3. The diet which is rich in flavonoids is also found to be effective in the regulation of brain function. However, there was no study predicting the inhibitory effects of selected dietary fruit flavonoids like Fisetin (from strawberries) and Hesperidin (from oranges) on vascular dementia targets. The main aim of the docking is to explore the possible interactions of these natural ligands against the targets and to compare the ligand-protein interactions with co-crystallized ligands and the calculation of binding energies. Docking results were analyzed and the best-docked conformation was chosen based on the number of conformations in a cluster and the estimated free energy of binding. Higher numbers of conformations and the lowest binding energy indicate better affinity of the compound to the targets. In this study, the three X-ray crystal structures of SDM co-crystallized with S-adenosyl methionine (SAM), S-Adenosyl Homocysteine Hydrolase (SAHH) co-crystallized with Neplanocin and ACHE co-crystallized with Aricept were used for docking.

The results of this study reveal that aryl structure of SAM, FST and HSP exhibited a high degree of similarity in the conformation and binding mode with SDM. Molecular docking studies predicted that hesperidin has best docking scores compared to fisetin when docked with target enzyme SDM (-8.67 & -5.94 respectively) when compared to respective crystal ligand SAM (-8.33). The structure of Neplanocin, FST and HSP exhibited a high degree of similarity in the conformation and binding mode with SAHH. Molecular docking studies revealed that hesperidin showed best docking scores compared to fisetin when docked with target enzyme SAHH (-7.68 & -7.14) compared to respective crystal ligands Neplanocin (-8.68 for SAHH). Molecular docking studies revealed that Hesperidin showed best docking scores compared to fisetin when docked with the target enzyme AChE (-10.76 & -6.09) when compared to respective crystal ligand Aricept (-10.95 for AChE). Molecular docking studies predicted that HSP has best docking scores when compared to FST that may be used as therapeutic adjuvant in the treatment of VaD.

Keywords:

Molecular Docking, Vascular dementia, Fisetin, Hesperidin, Neplanocin, Acetyl-cholinesterase co-crystallized ligands, Aricept, conformations, binding energies, S-adenosyl methionine.

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High throughput screening for small molecular drug candidates against amyloid-beta oligomers in Alzheimer's diseases

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Abstract:

Previously, Multimer Detection System (MDS) was developed for detecting multimers or oligomers in a given sample. Initially, MDS was optimized for prion oligomers in blood from hamster, mouse and sheep with prion diseases. Next, MDS was also devised to detect amyloid- β oligomers (A β O) oligomers in blood from patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD) with high sensitivity and specificity for early diagnosis. The results of MDS correlated well with other AD biomarkers, suggesting it as a reliable blood-based assay for the diagnose and monitoring AD. Here, MDS was modified to screen a chemical library of chemicals for selecting small molecular drug candidates in the therapeutic efforts against AD. A library of 1000 chemicals was selected. These chemicals were incubated with predetermined A β O prior to the MDS in comparison with the control (without drug). The assays were performed in duplicates. The hypothesis was to see the decreased MDS signals after the incubation with chemicals, breaking A β O into monomers. In order to verify the hypothesis, total concentrations of A β were also measured. Indeed, increased and decreased concentrations of A β and A β O were observed by total ELISA and MDS, respectively. These active chemicals were analysed for their reported toxicity and tested in vitro with AD related cell lines. In concentrations, several chemicals were selected as A β O breaker with minimal cytotoxicity, which will be further characterized in vivo model in near future.

Keywords:

Protein misfolding diseases, amyloid-beta, oligomers, Alzheimer's diseases, multimer detection system, High throughput screening

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the Multimer Detection System. a) Monomers are proteins with a single epitope that can be captured by an antibody attached to the surface of the plate. After the addition of a detection antibody, monomer proteins cannot be detected, because the single epitope is already occupied. b) Multimers with numerous epitopes can be detected by detection antibodies. The capturing and detection antibodies are different, but their epitopes overlap. ELISA Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

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Methodological Foundations of the Non-Material Nature of the Human Psyche

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Abstract:

In this paper, a number of outdated but still prevailing medical doctrines are critically reviewed, in particular, Hippocrates's hypothesis of the brain as a repository of all mental processes; I.M. Sechenov's hypothesis of the psyche as a derivate of the brain reflexes; I.P. Pavlov's hypothesis of the higher nervous activity as an equivalent of the psyche.

In his research, the author refers to studies of feral children, studies of memory and subliminal perception, discovery of mirror neurons and contemporary views of the academic science on information.

The author proves the non-materiality of the psyche and the role of the brain as a biological interface between the ideal and the real. The new approach would require changing the traditional paradigm as well as all our approaches to studying the psyche and treating mental disorders.

Key words:

Biological interface, brain, mind, non-material theory, psyche, psychic disorders.

Minorities in India; Cultural Analysis as Experimental System : Critical Evaluation of Scheduled Tribe Nomenclature

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Abstract:

India, like many of the countries of the postcolonial world, remains to a great extent an artificial construct of the colonial era. Beneath the surface, it is a country burdened with ethnic, religious and linguistic minorities. Even so, minority issues are increasingly taking centre stage in Indian politics, whether in the form of separatist movements, demands for increased social development, special privileges in education and employment opportunities and political representation. Many of these conflicts are yet to be resolved, and the challenge for India will be to put in place processes that enable minority problems to be discussed and resolved for the benefit of the country as a whole, while ensuring the collective survival of the many minority people who form an integral part of the country. In common parlance, the expression “minority” means a group comprising less than half of the population and differing from others, especially the predominant section, in race, religion, caste, traditions and culture, language, etc.

The Constitution of India uses the word ‘minority’ or its plural form in some Articles – 29 to 30 and 350A to 350B – but does not define it anywhere. Article 29 has the word “minorities” in its marginal heading but speaks of “any sections of citizens...have a distinct language, script or culture”. This may be a whole community generally seen as a minority or a group within a majority community. Article 30 speaks specifically of two categories of minorities – religious and linguistic. The Supreme Court rulings suggest that for the purpose of Article 30 a minority, whether linguistic or religious, is determinable with reference to a state and not by taking into consideration the population of the country as a whole. Incidentally, ‘scheduled castes’ and ‘scheduled tribes’ are also to be identified at the state/UT level as minorities. Sociologically the concept of minority groups refers to more than merely a numerical distinction. In sociology, members of minority group are disadvantaged when compared with the dominant group. It refers to a groups’ subordinate position within society rather than its numerical connotation. There are many cases in which a ‘minority’ is in fact a ‘majority’. Women are sometimes described as a minority group, while in many countries of the world they form the numerical majority. Because women tend to be disadvantaged in comparison with men (the majority) the term is applied to them. In apartheid period, blacks in South Africa constituted the minority but numerically they were the majority. This is because the term ‘minority’ signifies their subordinate and disadvantaged position in society.

Scholars have also used the term ‘minorities’ to refer collectively to groups that have experienced prejudice and discrimination at the hands of the ‘majority’ society. However, this over simplification may result in generalizations about discrimination and oppression that do not accurately reflect the experiences of specific groups in society. The prejudices and discrimination faced by the sexual minorities (LGBT), for example, may be completely different from the experiences of Dalits as a minority in India. The way in which a two different minority groups faces discrimination and oppression in society is far from identical. The only commonality between them is that they are treated not only as different but also inferior with the rest of the majority population. The cultural factors and the challenge of cultural analysis has (is to) developed as translation and mediation tools for helping make visible differences of interests, access, power, needs, desires, and philosophical perspective.

The comprehension of cultural factors of the various communities perceived by the Constitutional Drafters of India while classifying the communities as Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribe and Other Backward Classes at the national level and the classification of the same made by the State government authorities/ Committees, the verbalization and the translation process of words and thoughts reflected controversies due to pluralistic nature of the society. The present paper explores the utility of ‘cultural analyses’ as a mode of philosophical inquiry and try to find the labyrinth whose walls erected over a period simultaneously blind and guided the administrators and anthropologists. The constructed existing ethnographic knowledge of the various communities limits the space and the direction of their development. The administrative and legal structures forces one to move beyond without destroying the reproductive coherences of the issues following ‘experimental systems’

Public Health On Paralyzing Diseases And Their Traditional Treatments

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Abstract:

Paralyzing diseases were unknown in Black Africa despite outbreaks of meningitis, poliomyelitis, tuberculosis, sickle cell disease, complicated hypertension, diabetes, trauma etc ... and today HIV AIDS.

Black Africa thought of the mystical causes of paralysis, it took the arrival of the colonizers to have a real definition.

The risks of traditional nerve-related treatments often cause various degrees of burns and pressure ulcers.

Plants are used to either stimulate, revitalize the nerves

1) PDO f: crushed leaves = 50g

2) Djinakapāi f: crushed leaves = 50g

3) Spillanthus acmella f: asteraceae leaves powder 5 c to s

4) Mucuna pruriens f: fapaceae leaves powder 5 c to s

5) Chenopodium ambrosoid leaves powder 5 c to s

6) Citrus medica f: rutaceae powdered leaves 5c to s

The whole bagged, used in decoction of 10l in massage painting on the back, the limbs during 10 mn 3 times / J during several days according to the evolution of the state of the patient.

Ointment used:

Carapa oil procera 50ml → Shea oil 50ml → Boa fat 50ml → Elaeis guineensis f seed oil: palmaceae 150ml → Xylopia aethiopia powder f: annonaceae 2 c to c → Relaxant, antipyretic analgesic

Applied slightly after massage and brushing 3 times / day for several days depending on the evolution of the patient's condition.

Physiotherapy

Physical exercises are essential

In Africa, dance is physiological and cultural.

In Christian and animist circles ceremonies.

In Muslim circles the dance is reserved only for children.

In Africa, dance manifests joy and makes people forget worries.

Some children suffering from the effects of poliomyelitis, meningitis or other paralyzing diseases recover by dancing.

It has been noticed that some cases of paralysis are treated by traditional healers and complicate some cases by severe burns and bed-sores because they have no knowledge of anatomy, physiology, paralyzed limb is put on a boiling decoction which complicates the situation.

Traditional medicine is dangerous without modern medicine.

The talithakoumi center uses both medicines to help the population, especially the elderly, because the country does not have a retirement home.